

Funded by
the European Union

Project Number:
101095314

Project Acronym:
aUPaEU

Project title:
A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities

First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping

Version 0.3 – 09 May 2024

Deliverable 7.1

Deliverable

<i>Project Title</i>	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities
<i>Project Acronym</i>	aUPaEU
<i>Grant Agreement Number</i>	101095314
<i>Topic Id</i>	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-51 - Acceleration Services in support of the institutional transformation of Higher Education Institutions
<i>Programme:</i>	Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)
<i>Call:</i>	European Research Area (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01)
<i>Type of action:</i>	HORIZON-CSA HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
<i>Type of MGA:</i>	HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based [HORIZON-AG]
<i>Project starting date</i>	1 Jan 2023
<i>Duration</i>	60 months
<i>Partners</i>	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - UPC Karlsruher Institut für Technologie - KIT Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble- INP GRENOBLE Politecnico di Torino - POLITO Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu - AMU
<i>Work Package</i>	WP7 – Policy feedbacks, synergies and dissemination
<i>Deliverable Related No</i>	D7.1
<i>Deliverable No</i>	D18
<i>Deliverable name</i>	First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping
<i>Lead Beneficiary</i>	Politecnico di Torino (POLITO)

<i>Deliverable type</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R - Document, report <input type="checkbox"/> DEM - Demonstrator, pilot, prototype <input type="checkbox"/> DMP – Data Management Plan
<i>Dissemination level</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public – fully open <input type="checkbox"/> Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement <input type="checkbox"/> EU classified – RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444
<i>Deliverable due date</i>	30 Jun 2023
<i>New due date</i>	10 May 2024
<i>Approval date</i>	30 May 2024
<i>Status</i>	Approved
<i>Author(s) – Partner(s)</i>	Cristina Marullo - POLITO Arianna Alessia Armao - POLITO Jesus Alcober - UPC Sofia Beatrice Vercellone - POLITO
<i>Document version and delivery date</i>	v0.3 – 09 May 2024
<i>File name</i>	w aUPaEU_WP7_D7.1_First reporting on dissemination and sta...
<i>Keywords</i>	Communication, dissemination, stakeholder
<i>Abstract</i>	First reporting on Communication and Dissemination plans and stakeholders mapping

History of changes

<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Author(s) – Partner(s)</i>	<i>Reviewer(s) – Partner(s)</i>	<i>Description</i>
v0.1	1 May 2023	Jesus Alcober - UPC	Cristina Marullo POLITO	Table of contents
v0.2	1 June 2023	Cristina Marullo POLITO Arianna Alessia Armao - POLITO Jesus Alcober - UPC	Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble- INP GRENOBLE Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu - AMU	First draft
v0.2	15 June 2023	Cristina Marullo POLITO Arianna Alessia Armao - POLITO Jesus Alcober UPC		Final version
v0.3	09 May 2024	Jesus Alcober- UPC Sofia Beatrice Vercellone- POLITO Cristina Marullo- POLITO		consolidation of the received feedback and review

Abbreviation list

aUPaEU	A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities
EPICUR	European Partnership for an Innovative Campus Unifying Regions
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
D2.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D5 from WP2, Preliminary analysis and plan, outline of the acceleration services catalogue
D4.1	aUPaEU deliverable number D10 from WP4, Inventory, Action plan and preliminary set of processes
ERA	European Research Area
HEI	Higher Education Institution
MGA	Model Grant Agreement
Unite!	European university alliance of innovation, technology and engineering
YUFE	Young Universities for the Future of Europe
WP	Work Packages

Document Updates

This revised version of the deliverable incorporates the feedback from the European Commission, addressing the following inquiries:

- 1) The target audience of the project and the way it should be addressed according to its different profiles is not sufficiently addressed making unclear the reading of the table at page 14 about the meaning of the "all target" groups.
- 2) The stakeholders' mapping is then approached in theoretical terms in the following chapters without specifying to which categories the project will address its activities according to the different identified profiles.
- 3) Participation to events appears to be limited only to workshops organized by the project as no mentioning is made to possible external target events. Social media planning is correctly addressed as well as publications and press related activities. A revision of the document to better address the above mentioned weaknesses should be made. It is also suggested to consider to add in the plan the participation to the annual EARMA conference (in collaboration with the sister projects) given its high relevance for HEIs and its high information multiplication potential.

The document now explicitly addresses these comments.

Specifically, the document has been revised as follows:

- 1) A more detailed reference to the different profiles (audiences) has been added to the communication plan (table 2.1, pages 15-16). The different profiles are listed coherently with the stakeholder categories (see below, point 2) and with the standard categories proposed in the continuous reporting platform, to ensure coherence between planning activities and reporting activities
- 2) The stakeholder mapping section has been revised in order to better develop, within the broad identified stakeholder categories (i.e. core and extended stakeholders), different institutional

profiles. Stakeholder categorisation is now approached in macro-categories and subsequent distinctions. Descriptive tables (Tables 3.2 to 3.5) have been added for aUPaEU core stakeholders, and extended stakeholders in relation to different profiles. In coordination with WP2, WP4, WP5 and WP6, future ongoing evaluations will be made on the number of actual users and potential future users, within each category.

- 3) The description of the events in Table 2.1 has been extended to three main categories, including: a) participation to external target events (such as, the EARMA CONFERENCE, Unite! Dialogues, workshops organised by other alliances or projects, with the aim to raise awareness, engage and draw-in potential users); b) internal events, in two sub-categories, comprising seminars and workshops and training and coaching events. Participation in external events will be pursued in coordination with other alliances, specifically Unite!, EPICUR and the sister projects CATALISI and ACCELERATE FUTURE HEI.

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1 Introduction

aUPaEU kicked off in January 2023 after being granted from the European Commission in the framework of the [European Research Area](#). The whole project is based on the collaboration of five academic institutions belonging to two **European alliances**, Unite! and EPiCUR, under the [European Universities Initiative](#), **working closely** in the context of a coordinated support system for higher education institutions and their networks, by integrating and implementing acceleration services.

The very nature of the project is of general interest and has a quite unique potential. AUPaEU is the **first project** where two different alliances are successful in talking about potential competing initiatives. The final goal is to develop and test a set of acceleration services for the transformation of the research and innovation (R&I) activities of the two alliances, and of the involved partner institutions.

[Unite! – University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering](#) is a strategic, agile and dynamic alliance of nine European Universities based on shared values, vision and trust. It aims to be a driving force for technology and innovation, a multilingual transeuropean campus training the future experts of digital and green transition.

[EPiCUR - the European University Alliance](#) belongs to the first generation of European Alliances. It gathers nine partner Universities committed to pilot a new way of intensifying collaboration among Higher Education institutions through the creation of a European University.

aUPaEU involved partners are:

- From **Unite!**
 - [Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya · BarcelonaTech](#) (UPC), Spain - Coordinator
 - [IThinkUPC](#), Spain - Affiliated partner
 - [Grenoble INP - UGA Institut d'ingénierie et de management \(GRENOBLE INP\)](#), France - Partner
 - [Politecnico di Torino](#) (TORINO), Italy - Partner
- From **EPiCUR**
 - [Uniwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu](#), (UMA) Poland - Partner
 - [Karlsruher Institut für Technologie \(KIT\)](#), Germany - Partner

Following the Greek concept of the **agora**, the project will build a shared space where all stakeholders can offer and use **acceleration services** and, at the same time, contribute with their knowledge and expertise. Access to this space will be accessible, diverse and inclusive.

The ultimate goal of aUPaEU is thus to create **methodologies, sustainability plans, coaching services** and **tangible digital technologies** that will constitute an acceleration agora providing HEIs, HEI networks and Alliances with integrated, shared, and long-term **R&I strategies**. Here follows the detailed list of the expected outcomes:

- An agora of acceleration services, made up of a platform, the catalogue and the processes that run it
- Developing shared R&I strategies
- Enhancing cooperation with the surrounding R&I ecosystem
- Sharing of capacity, infrastructure, and resources
- Digital support and a consulting infrastructure to design investment plans
- Proposal of selected tools, methodologies and processes for coaching service and guidance for networks of HEI
- Sustainability plan for the agora of acceleration services

All transformations are intended to focus on **six major areas** of the HEI transformation agenda:

1. capacity, infrastructure and resource sharing
2. research career attractiveness
3. collaboration with R&I actors' ecosystem
4. open science
5. societal outreach
6. gender equality

All project outcomes will be met through the **collaborative efforts** of these five renowned research Universities with extensive expertise in **HEI networks and Alliances**: the resulting agora will therefore be **validated** by two Alliances' users, and is meant to serve as a model for other Alliances or networks of organisations to follow.

For what concerns aUPaEU structure, seven work packages (WP) will be in charge of the project fields of action, depicted in Fig 1.1:

Fig.1.1 aUPaEU work packages schema

2 Communication and dissemination plans

Starting from basic concepts, **dissemination** is the public disclosure of tangible project results to involve key actors and maximise project impact. **Communication** is a broader concept, a strategically planned process to share actions and results to a multitude of audiences, to raise project visibility. Being the **first network** of EU Alliances (a “network of networks”), raising aUPaEU visibility will be a key feature to spread results’ communication and dissemination, and to produce effective stakeholders and third parties’ engagement: their active involvement will indeed be essential as sources of knowledge in the first phases of the project, and to test, evaluate and monitor project outcomes.

aUPaEU communication plan will support the entire project evolution and all of its steps. In doing so, it will involve different audiences in different phases of the project. aUPaEU dissemination activities will specifically focus on the project outcomes, targeting potential users of the developed services: an **overall strategy** framework covering both fields is the most efficient way to make the most out of the available resources.

2.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

aUPaEU devotes significant resources to the dissemination and communication strategy, with the goal of **engaging and informing** core stakeholders, extended stakeholders, plus other end users in the project’s primary findings and activities since M1 through a set of outputs: press releases, newsletters and dedicated events.

All the aUPaEU WPs represent the **source** of primary information about project outcomes, and at the same time can leverage on WP7 communication infrastructures to accomplish their objectives.

This strategy encompasses seven key steps: (1) engaging stakeholders, (2) analysing requirements, (3) inspecting data, (4) defining business processes, (5) implementation, (6) conducting tests, and (7) disseminating outcomes. In particular, the outcomes of WP2-WP5 (Methodology towards R&I acceleration services, Investment and Sustainability Plan, Coaching Service and Guidance, Implementation), will **converge** in the agora of accelerated services and will be **tested** within WP6. WP6, (testing acceleration services and assessment of the user groups’ progress in the institutional transformations) will, in

particular, **assess** the validity of such outcomes involving users of aUPaEU acceleration services belonging to both core and extended stakeholders. Such a coordination and evaluation activity will enable WP7 to coherently disseminate the results to engaged stakeholders and new potential users. The above mentioned strategy is described in in D2.1

Communication and dissemination activities will be then linked to the **outcomes of all work packages**, in order to support the dissemination and to ensure the broadest possible **awareness** of all stakeholders of **upcoming and ongoing activities** and **outcomes**. WP7, in particular, is in charge of creating a **coherent and meaningful narrative** and **tailored messages** that explain the extension, depth and impact of project activities to various stakeholders and policy makers.

The main **goals** of aUPaEU communication and dissemination strategy will be:

- **Consolidating** project's outcomes for communication inside the community of partner universities
- **Providing** universally comprehensible information to the broadest public and mass media on the project goals and results
- **Increasing** the project visibility, promoting actors and stakeholders' cooperation and active involvement via dedicated actions
- **Selecting** the relevant channels to disseminate the results according to the interests/needs of the target audiences defined during and after the project
- **Creating** communication models that facilitate the involvement of actors and stakeholders
- **Harmonising** the project identity to the Unite! And EPiCUR ones
- **Monitoring** and evaluating the communication and dissemination results

Cooperation and the development of **synergies** with the Unite! and EPiCUR communities will serve as the foundation for defining an increasingly integrated communication plan and act as a lever for effective dissemination of the project results. During the first 6 months of project duration, the **intra-alliance** aspects of aUPaEU network will be emphasised in defining the communication and dissemination strategy.

2.2 Communication and dissemination activities (M1-M6)

2.2.1 Setup activities

2.2.1.1 Choice of the Domain and overall strategy

The web domain "widening.eu" has been registered in M1.

Coherently with the aUPaEU communication strategy, its web domain includes the terms "widening EU", to suggest the acceleration services offered in the agora and the main communication activities of the project. Here follows a brief list of reasons:

- **Clear and Memorable message:** The domain "widening.eu" provides a clear and memorable web address for the project's acceleration services. It effectively communicates the purpose and focus of the project, highlighting its commitment to widening participation and supporting institutional transformation.
- **Alignment** with the Project Objectives: The aUPaEU project aims to support HEIs in widening countries and facilitate their transformation journey. The domain "widening.eu" directly aligns with these objectives, emphasising the project's focus on promoting inclusivity and enabling institutions to overcome challenges in their digital transformations.

- **Relevance** to the European Context: The ".eu" domain extension signifies a European identity, which is fitting for a project that involves collaboration among European HEIs and aims to contribute to the development of the European Research Area. It reinforces the project's connection to the European higher education landscape and its commitment to fostering collaboration and innovation across borders.

- **Branding and Visibility:** The domain "widening.eu" can serve as a strong branding tool for the aUPaEU project. It creates a distinctive online presence that is easily recognizable and can help build awareness and visibility for the project and its acceleration services among stakeholders, including HEIs, researchers, policymakers, and the wider public.

- **Cohesion** with aUPaEU Project Goals: The aUPaEU project aims to create an acceleration agora—a virtual meeting place—for HEIs to connect with peers, stakeholders, and investors. By using the domain "widening.eu" for the project's acceleration services, it fosters a cohesive and unified platform where HEIs can access relevant resources, exchange knowledge, and collaborate on their institutional transformation journeys.

2.2.1.2 Network of aUPaEU contact points

Since the very beginning, aUPaEU communication and dissemination strategy devised an **integrated approach**, to establish the premises for the involvement and the **active involvement** of the **communities** of core and extended stakeholders. To this purpose, and in coordination with stakeholder mapping activities, a map of the **network of aUPaEU contact points**, has been developed in collaboration with partner universities. The group has been included as a section of the aUPaEU stakeholder map. The network of aUPaEU contact points incorporates, at the moment, the Communication Offices of Unite! and EPiCUR partner universities, thus potentially reaching both **core** and **extended** stakeholders. The aim is to inform and engage people in **crucial** positions in communications offices in the two alliances in aUPaEU project results and dissemination activities starting from M1.

Fig 2.1. Partners from Unite! and EPiCUR Alliances

2.2.2 Ongoing activities

Throughout the project evolution, aUPaEU overall communication and dissemination **actions** will consist of

- **creating** a real and efficient way of explaining
 - the concept of an agora of services
 - the project's main vision
 - the extension, depth, and impact of project activities
- **scheduling** communication and dissemination activities addressing each project result
- **selecting** the relevant channels to disseminate results depending on the involved contents and target audiences
- **monitoring** all communication activities (press clipping, event memoires)

Going more into detail, ongoing communication and dissemination **activities at M6** are:

- aUPaEU public **website** (<https://aupaeu.widening.eu/>), online from M1 of the project, will be the main channel for information and aims to reach all of the project's audiences through targeted communication material
- A preliminary agora website from M5 will show the stakeholders initial activities within the scope of the project, with diverse URLs such as <https://aupaeu.upc.edu> and in the following months <https://unite.widening.eu> and <https://epicur.widening.eu> for instance, on a case-by-case basis.
- **Twitter account** is also online from M1 to engage with policy makers, institutions, and partners, plus other HEIs and Alliances, and has posted 51 times
- **LinkedIn** account will soon be active as preferred channel to engage project partner's academic, administrative and student communities, together with other HEIs and Alliances, plus institutions in general; this will be particularly relevant to spread project results, outputs and services among the final users
- The project **logo has been** re-designed to give a glimpse of aUPaEU essence (an alliance of European University Alliances), while respecting Unite! and EPiCUR visual identities. It has been voted and approved from all the project partners by means of an online survey.
- The first **press release** will be finalised in M6, spreading the news of project kick-off, actions and purposes
- A first **newsletter** will be diffused in M6 to the network of contact points and the EU Commission, to inform about the process of involvement of third-party Institutions.
- A second **newsletter** will be diffused in M12 to the network of contact points and the EU Commission. The newsletter will communicate the kick off of WP2 activities and the ways and strategies to engage the community in the design of the catalogue of services

2.2.3 Planned activities (M6-M60)

In a short-term view, protocols and templates will be created for the creation of an **efficient** communication pipeline. aUPaEU website will feature the project with ad hoc sections for all aims, while the social media accounts will **extend** their contents and target audiences.

To **raise** awareness of the initiative on a local and international scale, multimedia contents will be created. aUPaEU will also attend and organise events, conferences, workshops, and fairs to give **assessments** of current practices and best practices.

Dedicated **press releases** and active **engagement** over social networks will be diffused during workshop events, to disseminate information on:

- The release of the acceleration services catalogue (from M14)
- The concept and the implementation of the MVS of the agora (M36), and the Mid-term workshop (M18), possibly on the occasion of a relevant EC event, (e.g., European R&I days)
- Final project outcomes (M57)

Table 2.1. **Updated plan** of upcoming aUPaEU communication and dissemination activities:

Activity	Purpose	Audience	Timing
Website	Being the main channel for spreading contents, services and activities, it will be constantly updated, also integrating social media access and sharing for single posts. A set of Google analytics instruments will be used to track and to report the engagement and the number of clicks of the website	University Alliances , single HEIs and research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances, HEIs and research institutions networks, Citizens, Public administrations, Industry and businesses, policy makers	M1-M60
Social media	LinkedIn and Twitter accounts will be designed to maximise the project actions undertaken and to engage in a two-way dialogue with core and extended stakeholders and end users	Faculty, staff and students of University Alliances, of single HEIs and of research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances, of HEIs and research institutions networks, Citizens, Public administrations, Industry and businesses, policy makers	M6-M60
E-newsletters	E-newsletters/Y will be issued to the aUPaEU community to report on latest activities and news	Staff and faculty of University Alliances and of single HEIs and of research institutions, Project partner universities, policy makers	M6, M12, M24, M48, M60
Press releases	Three press releases will be issued: one at the project's launch, one in the second half of the project's existence, and one to highlight the project's results. Press releases and dedicated social media activities will be issued on occasion of the workshop events.	Press offices of University Alliances, of single HEIs and of research institutions, Policy makers	M6, M30, M60

Publications	At least three articles will be published in peer-reviewed journals and specialised publications (open access)	Faculty and staff of University Alliances and of single HEIs and of research institutions, policy makers	M20-60
Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial workshop (ML7): outline of the acceleration services catalogue from D2.1 (M12) - Mid-term workshop (ML8): presenting the concept and the implementation of the MVS of the agora (M36), possibly in occasion of a relevant EC event, (e.g., European R&I days) - Final event (M57) 	Staff, Faculty and Students of University Alliances of single HEIs and of research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances, Public administrations, Policy makers	M12, M36, M57
Training and coaching events	aUPaEU will provide a series of training days for users on coaching and acceleration services. Coaching and training will be based on the acceleration services catalogue and they will provide a basis for testing and maintaining users engaged in aUPaEU's acceleration services	Actual users of aUPaEU acceleration services, such as Faculty, staff and students.	M15-M45
External Events	aUPaEU will participate in a number of events not organised by the project itself, to raise awareness, engage and draw-in potential users. These events include conferences (e.g. the EARMA conference), Unite! Dialogues, workshops organised by other alliances or projects. Participation in external events will also be pursued in coordination with sister projects CATALISI and ACCELERATE FUTURE HEIs.	Potential future users of aUPaEU acceleration services, such as Faculty, staff and students belonging to University Alliances, single HEIs and research institutions that are not affiliated to Alliances	M9-M60

3 Stakeholders mapping

Research and **Innovation** is an ever-growing field in terms of importance in the foreseeable future. This happens especially in **Europe**, where outstanding initiatives are taking place, such as the European Research Area (ERA), which is based on having a borderless market for R&I across the EU, or Horizon Europe, a crucial funding program helping with the idea of sustainability - a core EU value. All this considered, stakeholders' **participation** is crucial, them playing a significant role in making these goals achievable. Therefore, conducting a **study** to analyse them and consequently build a stakeholder's map is essential.

aUPaEU has as specific objective "07.1 **Engagement** with key stakeholders, including partner universities, funding agencies, policy makers and civil society and implement co-creation and feedback strategy to spread the project message".

The purpose of this section is then to **map** stakeholders by identifying them, selecting the ones participating in European R&I under the scope of aUPaEU project, which is based on European Alliances cooperation. Building such a map is intended to foresee the organisations that should be targeted depending on their characteristics, starting from the **analysis** developed in the mapping sequence.

aUPaEU core stakeholders are Universities belonging to two different European Alliances, Unite! and EPICUR: they will be the initial users **validating** project outcomes. They are considered as **core** stakeholders, whereas other Alliances or HIE will be the **extended** ones. At this point, the methodology proposed for core and extended stakeholders will **converge**.

The Stakeholder Map is a methodological **tool** aimed at **identifying** stakeholders affected to a greater or lesser extent by aUPaEU outcomes, in order to improve the **relational understanding** between them. In other words, the Stakeholder Map facilitates a more comprehensive analysis of the roles and interrelationships played by different actors at local, regional, state and international levels.

Subsection 3.1 presents the definition and analysis of available mapping models, plus the ones selected by aUPaEU - e.g., the power/interest grid. Subsection 3.2 shows the stakeholder mapping, defining the stakeholders and analysing their power and interest. Finally, section 3.3 details how to represent or visualise this information.

3.1 Analysis of stakeholder mapping models

This section is dedicated to stakeholders' **identification** and mapping models **analysis**. The aim is to understand the existing literature and to adapt this theoretical framework to our objective, which is the R&I environment within Europe and University Alliances.

First of all, we can adapt the **original definition** of Edward Freeman, who defines a stakeholder as any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organisation's objectives (Freeman, 1984). Being aUPaEU a project, the more appropriate **definition** of stakeholder is:

anyone who can affect or is affected by aUPaEU's outcomes

There are a number of **mapping models** in the literature that classify stakeholders in a four-quadrant matrix or more complex figures depending on the criteria. Analysing stakeholders against a set of criteria and plotting them on a graph enables decision making strategies based on the quadrant in which each stakeholder resides. Examples of stakeholders mapping models are the power/legitimacy/urgency (Mitchell et al., 1997), the power/interest grid (Mendelow, 1981), the influence/interest matrix from OGC (Sowden, 2011) and the knowledge/attitude matrix (Turner, 2014).

The **Mendelow matrix** is the model chosen for aUPaEU project. This is because it is simple enough to be manageable with the number of the considered stakeholders, and it leads with the power and interest dimensions, which can be objectively obtained, while its result shows how to manage the stakeholders.

The grid contains two axes: **power and interest**. The first represents how much **influence** stakeholders have over the project, whether they can help move it forward or halt its progress. Interest is the level of **expectation** they have for project outputs, i.e., if the project results are in line with their objectives and they can benefit from these results. We can allocate the stakeholders in four quadrants as they are represented in Fig 3.1:

- High Power/High Interest (key players to manage closely): We will need to fully engage with these individuals and exert considerable effort to meet their needs. Our relationship must remain strong. Manage closely, involve in tasks and decisions.
- High Power/Low Interest (keep satisfied by meeting their needs): We must work to keep these people satisfied and informed, avoiding communication overload. Engage and consult them, to increase their level of interest, delivering simple and clear messages.
- Low Power/High Interest (keep informed): We have to keep these people updated and in the loop. Share what's going on in the project.
- Low Power/Low Interest (low priority with minimum effort): We must keep an eye on these individuals or organisations, without overwhelming them with unnecessary communication.

Fig 3.1 Power/interest matrix

3.2 The stakeholder mapping process

The first step in the stakeholder mapping process is to **identify** stakeholders, obtaining a list of the organisations that are, or will be affected by the project. Several **techniques** may be useful, such as brainstorming, mind mapping, stakeholder lists or previous projects mappings. For what concerns aUPaEU, we have initially **collected** some information from UNITE.2020 and EPiCUR Research project, in order to get an initial list of organisations to be listed among project stakeholders. It is essential to clarify that, in this deliverable, we are dealing with **organisations** only, despite the stakeholder mapping will also consider individuals: within the agora of accelerations services, when introducing an individual from an organisation, the stakeholder **assessment** will be made at the individual level as well as the organisational level.

This section entails the research and **identification** of stakeholders involved in the European R&I ecosystem, always referring to the European Alliances initiative. The ecosystem is wide, involving a large number of core and extended stakeholders. This is why we identify the most relevant ones and propose a stakeholder’s taxonomy.

All this considered, in Table 3.1 are the macro categories stakeholders **involved** in research and innovation in Europe, and there are as well key stakeholders in aUPaEU project :

Table 3.1. Macro categories of aUPaEU stakeholders

No	Macro categories	Description
1	Citizens	They are the individuals who are motivated by research and development. These groups often are the end-users of research and

		innovation outcomes and may also be involved in research activities - e.g., being researchers. Here we also consider societal organisations and associations of users or researchers that are not acting as organisation members, but as individuals - e.g., groups advocating for sustainable and environmentally-friendly research and innovation practices.
2	HEIs and research institutions	These institutions are often the primary sources of new ideas and findings, and play a crucial role in the research and innovation ecosystem.
3	University Alliances	Those specific alliances surged from the European Universities Initiative, 2020 and 2022 Erasmus+ calls. By the end 2022, Erasmus+ had funded 44 European University alliances, representing 340 diverse higher education institutions from all over Europe.
4	HEI and research institutions networks	All remaining networks of HEIs or research institutions, which do not fall in the previous category "University Alliances".
5	Public administration	European Union (EU), national and regional governments are in charge of funding, setting policies and regulating research activities in their respective scope, be it regional, national or European.
6	Industry and businesses	Companies are key stakeholders in research and innovation, since they provide funding, commercialise innovations, and collaborate with academic and research institutions.

To clarify, stakeholders and their members may assume various roles based on the Agoras' business processes, as outlined in the deliverables of WP4, namely D4.1 "Inventory, Action Plan, and preliminary Set of Business Processes" and D4.2 "Report on research to business policy and roadmap approach," among others. For instance, individuals such as faculty, students, and staff of HEIs can take on the role of proposal seekers in the R&I matchmaking noticeboard. Users of the Agoras are individuals belonging to the macro categories in Table 3.1, that use or can use the Agoras.

3.3 The stakeholders mapping classification

The stakeholders' mapping visualisation is a powerful tool for representing and analysing the relationships, power, and interests of stakeholders within the acceleration services agora. It offers a clear understanding of stakeholder dynamics, facilitating management efficiency and strategic planning.

In the partner module of the agora, each partner's profile will include two additional fields: power level and interest level. These values range from zero – minimum level – to ten – maximum level. Power indicates the stakeholders' influence or impact on the agora, while interest represents their level of engagement and concern.

The visualisation consists of drawing the stakeholders in a matrix based on their assigned power and interest levels. This matrix provides tactical and strategic insights for managing and planning stakeholder interactions.

From a tactical perspective, the visualisation helps in day-to-day management by providing a clear overview of where each stakeholder is located in the matrix, following the steps stated in section 3.1., analysis of stakeholder mapping models. This knowledge enables tailored approaches and effective communication strategies to engage stakeholders based on their power and interest levels.

From a strategic perspective, the visualisation allows for analysis and projection of stakeholder dynamics in the medium term. It helps in identifying the desired evolution of stakeholders' influence and interest levels. This information guides the establishment of steps and actions to drive stakeholders towards the desired positions in the matrix.

For illustrative purposes, here follows a sample stakeholders mapping visualisation. The table contains a list of sample stakeholders from the above-mentioned six categories (Par. 3.1). Each stakeholder presents hypothetical levels of authority and interest. Afterwards, figure 3.2 depicts these values in the sample stakeholders mapping visualisation.

From a practical implementation of this stakeholders mapping, in the contacts database of the aUPaEU agora, this information will be stored. Currently there are more than 400 stakeholders stored in the contacts database of the aUPaEU agora.

#	Stakeholders	Level of Interest	Level of Power	Result
1	Trade Associations	6	1	Keep informed
2	Business Chambers	7	2	Keep informed
3	Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)	6.5	6.5	Key player
4	Manufacturing Company	7	4.5	Keep informed
5	Tech Corporation	9	7.5	Key player
6	Policy Think Tanks	8	5.5	Key player
7	Municipal Councils	3	4.5	Low priority
8	Regulatory Authorities	10	8	Key player
9	Government Agencies	9	6	Key player
10	Interdisciplinary Research Network	4.5	7	Meet their needs
11	Innovation Hub Association	6	9	Key player
12	Global Science Network	6	5.5	Key player
13	Research Partnership Forum	6	7	Key player
14	Academic Collaboration Network	7	8.5	Key player
15	International Research Consortium	9	7	Key player
16	National Academic Network	6	6	Key player

17	Consortium of Research Institutions	7	7.5	Key player
18	Association of HEIs	8	10	Key player
19	Research Foundation	4	6	Meet their needs
20	Institute of Science and Technology	5	8.5	Low priority
21	XYZ Research Institute	6	8	Key player
22	ABC University	7	9.5	Key player
23	Consumer Associations	4	4	Low priority
24	Non-profit Organisations	6	4	Keep informed
25	Community Organizations	4	5	Low priority
26	Local Residents	2	6	Meet their needs

Fig 3.2. Example of stakeholders mapping visualisation

Within the evolution of the agora, the stakeholders mapping visualisation will result from its outputs.

Overall, the stakeholders mapping visualisation enables the acceleration services agora to prioritise its engagement efforts, adapt communication strategies, and establish a roadmap for cultivating stakeholder relationships. By leveraging this visualisation, the agora can effectively manage stakeholders, foster partnerships, and achieve its objectives.

Stakeholder categorization is structured into macro-categories, guided by Table 3.1 and the three stakeholder distinctions outlined below. Collaborating with WP2, WP4, WP5 and WP6, ongoing evaluations will track the number of current users and potential future users within each category. These macro-categories and distinctions serve as the foundation for all WPs to conduct their activities. In the case of WP7, they shape the communication strategy. This strategy is two-fold: first, outward communication aims to inform and engage potential future users. Second, there will be continuous interaction with users. Coaching and training sessions will be particularly beneficial for those utilising aUPaEU services.

3.3.1 First distinction: core stakeholders

Core stakeholders are universities belonging to the European Alliances Unite! and EPiCUR, and that are either direct or indirect beneficiaries of the aUPaEU project.

Table 2 delineates the current core stakeholders (individuals) in aUPaEU project that are included in the database of the aUPaEU agora contacts, categorising them into HEI partners of Unite! and EPiCUR, and further distinguishing between widening and non-widening countries. Specifically, among the 221 current core stakeholders, 18% originate from widening countries, while 78% hail from non-widening countries.

Table 3.2. Current core aUPaEU stakeholders

	non widening	widening	Total
(EPiCUR) European Partnership for an Innovative Campus Unifying Regions	44	24	68
ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI		6	6
KARLSRUHER INSTITUT FUER TECHNOLOGIE	15		15
UNIVERSITÄT FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	7		7
UNIVERSITE DE HAUTE ALSACE	3		3
UNIVERSITE DE STRASBOURG	5		5
UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM	3		3
UNIVERSITY OF FREIBURG	7		7
UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHERN DENMARK	4		4
UNIwersytet im. Adama Mickiewicza w Poznaniu		18	18
(Unite!) University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering	137	16	153

	non widening	widening	Total
AALTO UNIVERSITY	5		5
INSTITUT D'INGÉNIERIE ET DE MANAGEMENT	16		16
KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HÖGSKOLAN	3		3
POLITECNICO DI TORINO	29		29
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT GRAZ	8		8
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DARMSTADT	4		4
UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA		3	3
UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA	72		72
WROCLAW UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY		13	13
Total	181	40	221

The core stakeholders, identified in Table 3.2, are involved in different projects that exist within each alliance. In Table 3.3 and Table 3.4, there is the list of Unite! and EPiCUR projects, which are one of the main sources of stakeholder engagement, to initiate the seven steps methodology for acceleration services development, described in D2.1

Table 3.3. List of current projects related to the Unite! alliance

No	Unite! Projects	Partners involved in each Project
1	Erasmus+	All nine Unite! partners
2	Unite!WIDENING	All nine Unite! partners AAVANZ Innovazion Agencja Rozwoju Aglomeracji Wrocławskiej S.A. Lisbon Technological Park Wrocławski Park Technologiczny
3	aUPaEu (A University Partnership for Acceleration of European Universities)	Universitat Politècnica De Catalunya Karlsruher Institut Für Technologie Institut Polytechnique De Grenoble Politecnico Di Torino Uniwersytet Im. Adama Mickiewicza W Poznaniu
4	ED-AFFICHE	All Unite! partners, Una Europa, 4EU+, CHARM-EU, EC2U, EU-CONEXUS
5	GreenChips-EDU in a nutshell	Graz University of Technology Politecnico Di Torino, Technische Universität Darmstadt Universitat Politècnica De Catalunya Grenoble INP-UGA

		Universidade De Lisboa Carinthia University of Applied Sciences
6	IDEM (Inclusion, Diversity, Equity in Mobility)	Technische Universität Darmstadt, Institut Polytechnique De Grenoble Aalto Korkeakoulusäätiö Sr Universitat Politècnica De Catalunya Universidade De Lisboa
7	H2020	Politecnico Di Torino Institut Polytechnique De Grenoble Universitat Politècnica De Catalunya Universidade De Lisboa Aalto Korkeakoulusäätiö Sr Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan Technische Universität Darmstadt
8	JPROV in a nutshell	Aalto Korkeakoulusäätiö Sr Karlsruher Institut Für Technologie Universidade De Lisboa Technische Universität Darmstadt Politecnico Di Torino Universitat Politècnica De Catalunya INP-UGA Grenoble

Table 3.4. List of Projects related to the EPiCUR alliance

No	EPiCUR Projects	Partners involved in each Project
1	Core Project	All nine EPiCUR partners
2	EPiCUR SHAPE-IT	Karlsruher Institut Für Technologie Université De Strasbourg Uniwersytet Im. Adama Mickiewicza W Poznaniu Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien Université De Haute Alsace Uha Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg Universiteit Van Amsterdam
3	EPiCUR Erasmus+ Pilot phase	All nine EPiCUR partners
4	EPIDI(The European Partnership for Innovation in Distant Internships project)	University of Strasbourg, Uniwersytet Im. Adama Mickiewicza W Poznaniu Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
5	FOCI(Future-proof Criteria for Innovative European Education)	EPiCUR partners: Universiteit Van Amsterdam Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis Université De Strasbourg European Consortium of Innovative Universities: Kaunas University of Technology

		Łódź University of Technology YUFE Partners: Maastricht University University of Antwerp University of Rijeka
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3.3.2 Second distinction: extended stakeholders

Those stakeholders from Table 3.1 that are non core stakeholders, are considered extended stakeholders: Citizens, HEIs and research institutions, University Alliances, HEIs and research institutions networks, Public administration, and Industry and businesses.

Table 3.5. Current extended aUPaEU stakeholders

	Non widening	Widening	Total
Industry and businesses	4	2	6
University Alliances	45		45
HEIs and research institutions	136	41	177
HEIs and research institutions networks	1		1
Public administration	5		5
Total	191	43	234

Table 3.5 illustrates the extended stakeholders in aUPaEU project that are currently included in the database of the aUPaEU agora contacts. Stakeholders with a supranational scope, such as European public administrations, or those representing countries in both widening and non-widening areas, such as university alliances, are categorised as non-widening stakeholders due to the emphasis on identifying stakeholders from widening countries.

Within this group, university alliances, single HEIs and research institutions that are or are not part of an alliance, will be directly impacted by the acceleration services that Agoras provide. Other categories, such as public administrations and industry-business may serve as potential users of Agoras. They also act as stakeholders that are indirectly impacted by Agoras, because of the acceleration of the institutions they interact with.

3.3.3 Third distinction: stakeholders in widening countries

Since one of the primary objectives of the aUPaEU project is to address the needs of stakeholders from widening countries in Europe, it is essential to differentiate between stakeholders from these widening countries and those from non-widening countries within the European context.

The widening countries in Europe are those that receive support from the European Union's Cohesion Policy to help reduce economic and social disparities. The list of widening countries includes Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia. These countries have

historically faced challenges in terms of economic development and infrastructure compared to other European Union member states. Widening countries have low participation rates in FP7 and H2020 projects.

3.4 The stakeholders management as an acceleration service

Stakeholder engagement is being considered as a potential addition to the initial catalogue of acceleration services offered by Agoras, and the stakeholders mapping classification tool described above has been integrated into the Agoras platform. Further information on this acceleration service can be found in D2.1.

For instance, at the time of reviewing the deliverable D7.1, it is noted that the aUPaEU Agora contains over 400 stakeholders, managing approximately 20 inquiries. Similarly, the Unite! Agora had over 1000 stakeholders, having handled more than 300 inquiries. These figures highlight the significant impact of this acceleration service.

4. References

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